

PREPARATION OF SI-C-O-N CERAMIC FIBERS FROM POLYCARBOSILANE (I) AMMONIATING OF POLYCARBOSILANE FIBERS

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SUMMARY: Si-C-O-N ceramic fibers can be obtained by ammoniating of PCS fibers. The ammoniate procession can be discussed in three stages: the first stage is from room temperature to 50°C; the second stage is in the range from 50 to 560°C; the third stage is from 560 to 1000°C. The content of nitrogen in the samples varied with the ammoniating time, temperature, and the concentration of ammonia. The process can be explained as a nucleophilic displacement of hydrogen and carbon by the attack of NH₂ radicals. The pyrolysis mechanism can be detected by IR, ²⁹Si MAS-NMR and elemental analysis.

KEYWORDS: Si-C-O-N ceramic fibers ammoniating polycarbosilane Pyrolysis

INTRODUCTION

Processing of organosilicon polymers to ceramic fibers provides a route to fine diameter, textile grade fibers. Woven and knitted structures are desired to reinforce ceramic matrix or metal matrix composites which can overcome the brittle, catastrophic failure of monolithic ceramics[1].

Nicalon ceramic fibers are converted from polycarbosilane (PCS) through melt spinning, cross-linking, and pyrolysis [2]. The normal structure of PCS is $-(\text{-CH}_3\text{HSiCH}_2\text{-})_x-$ [3], though the actual structure is complexly branched and with CH₃HSiCH₂ and Me₂SiCH₂ functionality contained. The most active bond in PCS molecule is Si-H due to its low bond strength •315kJ/mol•, the next is Si-C •319.2kJ/mol•. When the PCS was heated in an ammonia atmosphere, the molecule may first decompose [4, 5].

As the temperature is high enough to activate the Si-CH₃, the PCS will also decompose in ammonia atmosphere in the following ways.

Although ammonia is kinetically stable in the gas phase due to its high N—H bond strength •460kJ/mol•, it is thermodynamically unstable above 200•. It decomposed readily on many surfaces [6, 7]. When the temperature raised to 500•800•, ammonia may decomposed as the following modes.

When the PCS pyrolyzing in the ammonia atmosphere, the thermal decomposition of the polymer catalyzes the decomposition of ammonia. The nitrodatation has been explained as a nucleophilic displacement of carbon and hydrogen by ammonia. Just on this point, the nitrodatation of PCS is a way to produce Si₃N₄ powders by Gary T. Burns and Grish Chandra, etc. In this paper, the nitrodatation of PCS fibers to produce Si-C-O-N fibers is discussed.

EXPERIMENT

In order to keep the fibril shape unchanged during nitrodatation, the PCS fibers were first cross-linked in the air at 200• for about 4~10hr. The nitrodatation of PCS was carried out in a quartz tube furnace at 400~800•for 6~12hr, the gas flow of ammonia was 20~50ml/min. After nitrodatation, the ammoniated fibers were treated at 0.5•/min to 800•, 3.5•/min to 1250•, then kept for 1hr at 1250• in nitrogen. The average tensile strength of the fibers is more than 1.60GPa; some of them reached up to 3.0GPa.

The tensile strength of the ceramic fibers was tested at room temperature according to Japanese industrial standard R 7601-1986. Elemental compositions of the ceramic fibers were determined by different methods: carbon and hydrogen by element analyzer model PE-2400II(P. E. Co., USA.); nitrogen by N/O determinator (Model TC-436, LECO Co., USA.); silicon and oxygen by neutron activation analysis; boron by inductively coupled plasma torch-auger electron spectroscopy (Model PS-6, Baird Co.). Magnetic resonance spectra of ²⁹Si nuclei was obtained on finely ground powders at 8.45Tesla, corresponding to a ²⁹Si resonance frequency of 79.4MHz, using a FT-NMR instrument and magic angle sample spinning.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The process of nitrodatation was detected by TG. As shown in Fig. 1, the process of nitrodatation can be discussed in three stages: The first stage is from room temperature to 50•. During this

stage, the weight of the fibers increased drastically due to two factors: The main reason is the physical absorption of the preceramic fibers because of its high specific surface. Another reason is the reactions between NH_3 and the reactive functionalities on the surface of the fibers. The weight gain is 8.0wt% in total.

Fig. 1. Thermogravimetric curves for ammoniating of PCS fibers with the temperature changed.

Fig. 2. Thermogravimetric curves for ammoniating of PCS fibers at the same temperature.
B: TG curve C: Temperature.

The second stage is in the temperature range from 50 to 560°C. In this stage, there is a continuous slow weight loss, the fibers lost about 7.5wt% of its weight because of the disabsorption of NH_3 which was absorbed by physical absorption. In spite of the disabsorption, by the end of this stage, there is still 0.5wt% of weight increase in contrast to the original weight. These can be owned to the irreversible reactions. The third stage is in the temperatures from 560 to 1000°C. During this stage, the weight loss of the fibers reached up to 20wt%. This is because the decomposition of PCS started when the temperature reached up to 400°C. With the temperature elevated, the decomposition of the PCS became more drastically, and the evolution of small molecules such as CH_4 and H_2 increased relatively.

Fig. 2 is the thermogravimetric curves for ammoniating of PCS at 400°C. As shown in the graph, first, there is a drastically weight increasing when the temperature was increased from room temperature to 380°C, the weight increase is about 7.0wt% due to the physical absorption; then follows a weight loss during the temperature being increased from 380-400°C, it lost about 6.7wt% of its weight; after that, when keeping the temperature at 400°C, the sample has a continuous stable weight increase. At this temperature, when the time lasted for 4hrs, the weight increase reached up to 6.5wt%. This is because of the reactions between Si-H, Si- CH_3 and NH_3 .

As shown in Fig.3, compared to the original PCS, there is no difference to the characteristic absorption in the infrared spectrum except the peak of Si-H at 2100cm^{-1} minimized. When the temperature reached up to 600°C and 800°C, the case is different, the characteristic absorption at 2100cm^{-1} disappeared while the peaks at 1250cm^{-1} minimized, broad N-H stretches at 3400cm^{-1} and 1080cm^{-1} and Si-N-Si asymmetric stretch at 900cm^{-1} were observed. The result suggests that at 400°C, the

Fig. 3 Infrared spectra of PCS fibers ammoniated at different temperature

nucleophilic displacement of Si-H by NH_3 started, when the temperature reached up to 600°, the displacement of Si- CH_3 by NH_3 is begun. The result also suggests that at lower temperature such as 400°, using NH_3 cross-linking the PCS fibers should be possible, but at higher temperature, the ammoniating of PCS fibers would cause drastically backbone changes in the polymer. The results are partly consistent with that of Gary T. et al[5]. The case can also be side testified by the elemental analysis.

As shown in Table 1., at 400°, in contrast to the original PCS fibers, the increasing of nitrogen is trivial, and the decreasing of carbon is only 0.3wt%. But when the temperature reached up to 600°, the loss of carbon is remarkable. On the other hand, the content of nitrogen was increased while hydrogen decreased. The decreasing of silicon with the ammoniating temperature is due to the decomposition of PCS and the evolution of small pieces like Me_3SiH , Me_2SiH_2 , SiMe_4 and MeSiH_3 [4].

Table 1: Composition of PCS fibers ammoniated at different temperatures.

Polymer	Ammoniating temperature (K)	Elemental analysis (wt%)				
		Si	C	O	N	H
PCS fiber		42.7	35.4	15.5	<0.1	6.3
PCS fiber / NH_3	673	42.0	35.1	16.3	3.8	4.8
PCS fiber / NH_3	873	36.5	29.6	18.2	12.5	3.2
PCS fiber / NH_3	1073	35.5	22.5	19.4	18.2	2.1

The content of nitrogen in the ammoniated fibers was dependent on the initial temperature of ammoniating, the concentration of ammonia, and the time of ammoniating, the results were shown in Fig. 4, Fig. 5, Fig. 6. As the temperature of ammoniating elevated, or the time lasted, or the concentration of ammonia increased, the content of nitrogen increased.

As shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5, the content of nitrogen increased proportionally with the temperature of ammoniating and the concentration of ammonia. The content of nitrogen at

600• is 12.5wt% in contrast to 360• is only 2.1wt%. When the concentration of ammonia in the atmosphere is 10vol%, the content of nitrogen in the fibers is only 2.0wt%, when the content of ammonia increased to 100vol%, the content of nitrogen slowly increased to 3.2wt%. If the temperature was held at 450•, and the concentration of ammonia was kept on 40vol%, but the ammoniating time varied, the case was different.

Fig. 4: Content of nitrogen at different temperature.

Fig. 5: Content of nitrogen for different concentration of ammonia.

As Fig. 6 told us, at the first hour, the content of nitrogen increased drastically with the reacting time, nitrogen in the samples increased from 0.1wt% to about 2.5wt%. But in the following hours, the nitrogen increased more slowly than that of the first hour, the weight increase is about 2.5wt% altogether. This is because the ammoniating of PCS fibers was first happened to the reactive bonds at the surface or the surface in big holes. At this stage, the speed is only controlled by the reaction itself. When ammonia molecules penetrated into the inner parts of the fibers, the inner ammoniating is begun. At this stage, the speed of ammoniating is not only controlled by the reaction itself, but also by the penetration of the NH_3 .

The elemental analysis is also consistent with both the IR and ^{29}Si NMR studies. As shown in Fig. 3, the content of nitrogen varied with the temperature of ammoniating is consistent with the infrared spectra. IR analysis for the fibers ammoniated at 400• shows that only the Si-H absorption at 2100 cm^{-1} minimized in contrast to that of the original fibers, the characteristic absorption of N-H stretches at 3400 cm^{-1} and 1080 cm^{-1} and Si-N-Si asymmetric stretch at 900 cm^{-1} is not obviously observed. However, by 600•, broad N-H stretches at 3400 cm^{-1} and 1080 cm^{-1} and Si-N-Si asymmetric stretch at 900 cm^{-1} were observed in all the samples. In addition, the Si- CH_3 stretches at 1250 cm^{-1} disappeared. The result suggests the loss of the Si-H and Si-C polymer backbone for PCS and the formation of a Si-N type residue, respectively.

Fig. 6: Content of nitrogen for different reacting time.

Fig. 7: ^{29}Si MAS-NMR spectrum of powdered Si-C-O-N ceramic fiber.

As shown in Fig. 7, solid-state ^{29}Si MAS-NMR also suggests the formation of a Si-N bond for the ammoniated fibers pyrolyzed at 1250°C . Ceramic fibers from the ammoniated PCS fibers which pyrolysis in ammonia at 400°C for 8hrs, peaks at -44.4ppm (SiN_4), -51.5ppm ($\bullet\text{-Si}_3\text{N}_4$) and -64ppm ($\text{Si}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}$) were observed in the ^{29}Si NMR spectrum. They correspond to silicon bonded to nitrogen. Thus, the conversion involves: first, the removal of hydrogen, then at high temperature ($>600^\circ\text{C}$), the removal of carbon. Presumably, the process can be explained as a nucleophilic displacement of hydrogen and carbon by the attack of NH_2 radicals.

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